

D6.2

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package

WHITE

October 2022

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AUTHORS (Organisation)	Antonia-Areti Kalimeri (WHITE), Pinelopi Kaslama (WHITE)
REVIEWERS	Iris Vural Gursel (WR)
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1. INTRODUCTION.....	10
2. VISUAL IDENTITY	11
2.1 Project logo	11
2.2 Project templates	13
3. PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	17
3.1 Leaflet	17
3.2 Poster	19
4. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED WEBSITE	20
4.1 Technologies used for the creation of the website	20
4.2 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website sitemap.....	21
4.2.1 Homepage.....	22
4.2.2 About us.....	23
4.2.3 Resources.....	28
4.2.4 Networking	30
4.2.5 News.....	33
4.2.6 Events.....	34
4.2.7 Contact us.....	34
4.3 Roles and content management	35
4.4 Privacy Policy.....	35
5. SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS	36
6. PROMOTIONAL VIDEO.....	37
7. PROJECT’S GENERAL PRESENTATION.....	38
8. PUBLICATIONS	39
9. CONCLUSIONS	40
10. ANNEX.....	41
Annex I – Website’s privacy policy	41

Annex II- Network of Interest online registration documents 45

Declaration of Acceptance for the Network of Interest 45

NoI Terms of reference..... 46

Information Sheet and consent form..... 50

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package	10
Figure 2. EU flag and disclaimer	11
Figure 3. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo.....	12
Figure 4. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo different editions	12
Figure 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED colour palette	13
Figure 6. Presentation template	14
Figure 7. Presentation template - first slide	14
Figure 8. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deliverable template	15
Figure 9. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deliverable template cover	16
Figure 10. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED letterhead template.....	17
Figure 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet (1)	18
Figure 12. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet (2)	18
Figure 13. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED poster.....	19
Figure 14. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website sitemap	21
Figure 15. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Homepage (1)	22
Figure 16. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our mission page (1).....	24
Figure 17. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our mission page (2).....	24
Figure 18. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (1)	25
Figure 19. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (2)	25
Figure 20. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (3)	26
Figure 21. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (4)	26
Figure 22. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED The workplan page.....	26
Figure 23. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our team page	27
Figure 24. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Advisory Board page	27
Figure 25. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Deliverables page.....	28
Figure 26. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Newsletter page	29
Figure 27. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Promotional material page	29
Figure 28. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Scientific publications page	30
Figure 29. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Networking page (1)	30
Figure 30. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Networking page (2)	31
Figure 31. The members of the Network of Interest page	31
Figure 32. Registration process to the Nol _step 1	32
Figure 33. Registration process to the Nol _step 2	32
Figure 34. Registration process to the Nol _step 3	33
Figure 35. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Contact us page	34
Figure 36. Social media accounts	36
Figure 37. Recent posts.....	37
Figure 38. General presentation (1)	38
Figure 39. General presentation (2)	38
Figure 40. First press release	39

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Key words depicted in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's logo	11
Table 2. Technologies used for the website	20
Table 3. Technologies used for the hosting service	20
Table 4. E-mail service information	21
Table 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED social media accounts	36

ABBREVIATIONS

CIRCE	Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos
CU	Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NoI	Network of Interest
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
SMA_s	Social Media Accounts
WEcR	Wageningen Economic Research
WFBR	Wageningen Food and Biobased Research
WHITE	White Research SRL
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WR	Wageningen Research

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents in detail the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package. The promotional package constitutes the official project's material that will assist the consortium partners during the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy (D&C). In particular, the material will give more information around the concept, the approach, the goals, the impact, the team of the project and will disseminate the project's activities and interesting outcomes and results. Lastly, besides giving a description, the document includes plenty of snapshots that depict the produced promotional material.

The current document includes:

Chapter 1: Overview of the promotional package.

Chapter 2: Presentation of the visual identity of the project.

Chapter 3: The leaflet, poster, and Letterhead.

Chapter 4: Detailed presentation of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website including a brief description of the website management and presentation of the privacy policy of the site.

Chapter 5: This paragraph introduces the social media accounts.

Chapter 6: This section mentions the promotional video.

Chapter 7: This section includes the project's general presentation.

Chapter 8: In this chapter are described the publications related to the project.

Chapter 9: Conclusions

The Annex of this report includes:

- The websites' privacy policy (Annex I)
- The Network of Interest (NoI) online registration documents (Annex II)

1. Introduction

The D&C strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED was thoroughly described in D6.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan”. The strategy will be followed throughout the duration of the project to promote the vision, the outcomes and spread the project’s messages to the targeted stakeholders. This report includes the promotional material produced in the framework of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The material was developed by M5 and will be used to support the consortium partners during the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package includes a variety of material aiming to engage citizens with various backgrounds and characteristics. For instance, scientific publications will target professionals relevant to the sector, the social media will enable us to establish synergies with other initiatives and the promotional video will help us reach the wider public. The material will be used by the consortium partners during their participation in internal and external events, while it will be also available online.

The figure below depicts the basic promotional package of the project:

Figure 1. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package

The promotional package started with the development of the project’s logo and the visual identity and continued with the creation of the official leaflet, poster, and letterheads. In addition, a Power Point (.ppt) template for the project’s presentations, as well as a Word document (.doc) template for the project’s reports were also circulated to the consortium. The social media accounts (SMAs) were established by M2 and will remain active throughout the project. The online presence of the project was completed with the creation of the official web-portal which will constitute the main online dissemination channel for the results. The promotional video aiming to raise awareness will be created by M15, while a bi-annual Newsletter will be distributed from M6 up until the end of the project. Finally, several other forms of publications will take place within the next three years including dedicated press – releases, scientific papers, articles etc.

In the following chapters more details are given for the items comprising the promotional package of the project.

2. Visual identity

The establishment of a unique visual identity for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is fundamental for its recognition and eventually for the successful engagement of the targeted stakeholders. The graphical identity should be always followed to ensure consistency in the promotional material. In particular, the official project logo, the EU flag and the respective disclaimer (see figure below) should be always depicted, while all documents should adapt to the specific graphical elements (colours, fonts etc.). To this aim, from the beginning of the project, the dissemination manager developed the visual identity of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED which will be used during its lifecycle.

Figure 2. EU flag and disclaimer

2.1 Project logo

The logo is the main graphical element which is inseparably connected to the project, and constitutes the strongest visual item that raises awareness about SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The logo should be depicted in all the material produced in the framework of the project, and therefore was designed at the beginning (M1).

The logo is designed in a modern, fresh-looking style that aims to capture the key elements of the project. The colors and graphical items were aligned to the main key words that were selected by the dissemination manager.

Key words used to produce the logo:

Table 1. Key words depicted in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's logo

Key words considered during the preparation phase	Key words translated into the final logo
Certification schemes and business-to-business labels	Stamp
Bio-based products	Leaf, color (green)
Sustainability, circular economy	Leaf, color (green)
Industrial biobased systems	Gear

Initially, 7 different logo options were created. After the partners' valuable feedback, which was given through a voting process, the consortium partners agreed on the final logo that is depicted in Figure 3 with its different editions in Figure 4.

Figure 3. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo

Figure 4. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo different editions

Figure 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED colour palette

2.2 Project templates

Templates function primarily as the basis for drafting reports, creating deliverables, and making presentations under the project's activities. To support all partners during the dissemination and communication activities and to ensure consistency, three different templates have been developed which were eventually circulated to all consortium partners who participate in the project.

1. **A presentation template (.ppt template):** This template (see Figure 6) will be used by all partners to present their progress in internal meetings, project events (such as monthly meetings, WP level presentations, workshops, Nol meetings etc.) and in external events (such as conferences, meetings of related projects etc.). In the first slide, the template includes the logo of the project, the consortium partners, and the EU funding acknowledgment (see Figure 7).
2. **A report template (.doc template):** This template (see Figure 8) is used by all partners for the deliverables and reports produced in the framework of the project. In the first page, the template includes the logo, the EU acknowledgement, the title of the report, the organisation that drafted the report, the date and the main image used in the promotional material (see Figure 9).
3. **Letterheads template (.doc):** This template is designed to be used by the partners for sending official invitations to external stakeholders in the framework of project activities. The Letterhead of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED which is designed and based on the visual identity of the project is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 6. Presentation template

Figure 7. Presentation template - first slide

Figure 8. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deliverable template

Figure 9. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deliverable template cover

Figure 10. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED letterhead template

3. Promotional material

3.1 Leaflet

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet is a trifold document that gives more information about the concept and the objectives of the project (see Figure 11 and Figure 12). The leaflet is designed based on the graphical identity of the project, and the consortium partners can print and distribute it during physical events and activities. In addition, the leaflet is openly available for downloading through the project's website ([here](#)). The sections of the leaflet are briefly described below:

The first page of the leaflet includes the logo and the title of the project, as well as the basic promotional image.

The project: This section includes a very short description of the project.

The challenge: The main challenge which the project aims to tackle is briefly described in this paragraph.

Who will benefit from the project: This section outlines the targeted stakeholders of the project.

The vision: The vision and the main objectives of the project are enlisted in this section allowing the reader to dive into more details.

The impact: This section presents the project's contribution and impact towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable biobased industry.

Project ID: This section includes some key information about the project's identity (e.g. Title, GA number, coordinator, programme, call etc.)

The team: This part of the leaflet depicts the consortium partners' logos.

Contact info: A section in the leaflet is dedicated to the established communication channels of the project (SMAs, website, e-mail).

The project

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption.

OUR TEAM

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.circe.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

Sustainability Certification *for* Biobased Systems

www.sustcert4biobased.eu

Project ID

PROJECT NAME:	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED "Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems"
GRANT AGREEMENT:	101059785
PROGRAMME:	Horizon Europe
TYPE OF ACTION:	HORIZON-CSA
START DATE:	1 June 2022
DURATION:	36 months
EU CONTRIBUTION:	1,999,750.00
COORDINATOR:	Stichting Wageningen Research

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CONTACT US

info@sustcert4biobased.eu

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the European Union

Figure 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet (1)

The Challenge

The future belongs to biobased products! However, a successful transition from fossil to renewable biological resources should always ensure the environmental, social and economic sustainability. To this end, a plethora of certifications and labels have been developed to allow traceability and transparency of sustainability impacts along the value chains and trades. Today, it is essential to evaluate the effectiveness and the robustness of these tools, support their harmonization and recognize their critical role to ensure a sustainable circular bioeconomy. This is where SUSTCERT4BIOBASED comes into play!

Our impact

Contribute towards establishing circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry by:

- Improving and harmonizing existing international and EU certification schemes
- Promote and boost the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and labels
- Increased transparency and traceability of sustainability impacts along biobased value chains

Who will benefit from the project?

- ✔ Sustainability certification scheme and label owners, standardization organizations and certification bodies
- ✔ Governments & policy makers
- ✔ Industrial biobased value chain actors
- ✔ Regional bioeconomy & sustainability actors
- ✔ Non-governmental organisations
- ✔ Academia & scientific community
- ✔ General public

Our vision

- 01** Review and analyze the existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and labels for biological resources and biobased products
- 02** Develop a monitoring framework to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of existing certifications schemes and labels
- 03** Testing the monitoring framework on the existing schemes/labels and identifying their strengths and weaknesses
- 04** Gather data and create a database on the global trade flows for biological resources and for biobased products and level of certification
- 05** Assess the costs and benefits (including internalized environmental and social ones) from the adoption of certification schemes and labels and evaluate their feasibility
- 06** Provide recommendations tailored to key target groups for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels

Figure 12. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet (2)

3.2 Poster

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED poster is a one-page document that can be printed by the partners and be presented in physical events in the framework of the project. The poster is designed based on the visual identity of the project and focuses more on attracting citizens' attention and eventually engage them through the project's website and social media accounts. A brief description of the project is provided in the poster, while special focus is given to the 4 key stakeholder groups for which recommendations will be offered in this project. The poster can be also downloaded through the project's website ([here](#)).

Figure 13. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED poster

4. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Website

4.1 Technologies used for the creation of the website

The website is developed by using state-of-the-art technologies and is designed in a user-friendly way.

Table 2. Technologies used for the website

Technologies used for the website	
Dynamic content management system	WordPress
Backend programming language	PHP, version 8.1
Database	MySQL version 5.7.39
WordPress theme	Avada
Integration with services	Google Webmaster Search Console, Google Analytics, Mailchimp API for newsletters

Table 3. Technologies used for the hosting service

Technologies used for the hosting service	
Server OS	CentOS 7
Hosting management system	cPanel, version 106.0.7
Amazon Web Services	API configuration used for weekly backups
Firewall: Yes	ConfigServer Security & Firewall
WordPress Toolkit	Yes. Deluxe version
Features	3 GB of disk space 2 databases 2 subdomains (e.g. eshop.website.gr) Unlimited traffic

Table 4. E-mail service information

E-mail service information
3 users, e.g. info@domain.name, user1@domain.name, user2@domain.name,
0,5 GB each or 1,5 GB common data pool
RoundCube Webmail interface
Configuration for email client access, e.g. Microsoft Outlook, Mozilla Thunderbird

4.2 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website sitemap

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website (<https://sustcert4biobased.eu/>) will be the main online dissemination channel of the project. The website will increase the project’s visibility to the identified key stakeholders but also to the wider audience as it will be openly accessible to everyone. The site is designed to maintain a fresh-looking and eye-catching interface with the aim to be user friendly for all the types of stakeholders. As it is depicted in the following sitemap, the website will include information regarding the mission and the goals of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, as well as the concept, the workplan and the approach followed within the project’s lifecycle. Additionally, it will include the project’s news and events, as well as relevant news and events from the bioeconomy sector. All project’s dissemination material and public results will be easily findable, while a separate section will be dedicated to the Nol. The SMAs, as well as the newsletter subscription, will be displayed in key sections of the site in order to attract new subscribers and followers.

Below you may find the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED sitemap:

Figure 14. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website sitemap

4.2.1 Homepage

The Homepage is designed aiming to captivate the users' interest. Some brief information for the project is instantly provided to the user and redirect him/her to other dedicated sections of the website. The news, recent events and the latest tweets are also displayed. Additionally, the SMAs and the subscription to the Newsletter are highlighted aiming to attract as many followers/subscribers as possible. In order to further engage the users to the project's Newsletter, a pop-up window with an invitation to our Newsletter appears the first time a visitor enters the website. An invitation button to subscribe to the NoI is also present, as well as a button to further explore our sister projects. Furthermore, the partners' logos appear in the Homepage with a link to their website. Finally, the EU acknowledgment and the privacy policy are visible in the footer of the page. Below are presented some snapshots from the Homepage (online [here](#)).

Figure 15. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Homepage (1)

Figure 16. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Homepage (2)

4.2.2 About us

This is the main section where the project is presented to the visitors. The users may find information about the project’s mission and goals. The main challenge the project aims to address is highlighted and the concept is described. The visitor may find a detailed elaboration on the approach that will be followed by the partners throughout the duration of the project, as well as the project’s workplan. Finally, the team members are presented, and a page is also dedicated to the members of the Advisory Board which will be finalised after deciding its final composition. Snapshots from the “About us” section are presented below (online [here](#))

Figure 16. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our mission page (1)

Figure 17. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our mission page (2)

The Challenge

Sustainability certification schemes and eco-labels are fundamental tools to ensure the sustainability of global production. Although their role in European bioeconomy has grown over the last few decades, still there are a lot of challenges that needs to be addressed in order to be further adopted in the market:

- Different approaches of certification schemes regarding the system operating requirements (e.g sustainability criteria, verification procedures etc)
- Challenging for businesses to select and identify the schemes that are most credible
- Different schemes/labels put emphasis on different environmental impacts of the products

Figure 18. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (1)

Figure 19. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (2)

The approach

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has designed a solid methodological approach to support the wider adoption of certification schemes and labels for biobased products in European industries.

The steps that will be followed through the duration of the project:

▼ **Analysis of sustainability schemes and labels for biological resources and biobased materials and products**

The project begins with a systematic review of the existing certification schemes and labels. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will follow a holistic sustainability approach and will examine the schemes in 4 different dimensions: 1) environmental 2) social 3) economic 4) governance

▼ **Data and figures on volumes of biological resources and biobased materials and products in global trade flows distinguishing between certified and uncertified**

Currently a mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products is missing. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will fill this gap by gathering information and creating a database of the imports and exports from the EU, the geographical distribution, as well as the status regarding their certification.

▼ **Monitoring system for sustainability certification schemes and labels**

In order to ensure the effectiveness and robustness of the schemes, and promote a comprehensive system, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will develop a

Figure 20. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (3)

Project Factsheet

Project title: Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems

Project acronym: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

Type: HORIZON-CSA

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Grant Agreement n°: 101059785

Duration: 36 months

Total cost: 1,999,750.00

Figure 21. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our concept page (4)

The activities under WP6 will communicate and disseminate SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results among th... main target groups, will facilitate interaction with relevant stakeholders through the creation of the Network of Interest, will establish synergies and will maximise exploitation and sustainability of the project's results.

▼ **WP7: Management and coordination**

This WP will ensure the effective management and coordination of the consortium and will ensure the high quality and on-time delivery of the project's results.

Figure 22. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED The workplan page

Figure 23. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Our team page

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Advisory Board will act as a consultation body providing the project with feedback, strategic recommendations, contribute to the project dissemination through their wider stakeholder communication channels, and to maximise and sustain the project results.

The members of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Advisory Board are presented below:

	<p>Name</p> <p>Role/Position</p> <p>Organization</p>		
---	---	---	---

Figure 24. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Advisory Board page

4.2.3 Resources

This section will include the material and results produced in the framework of the project, as well as the projects with which we have established synergies.

This section includes:

1. Deliverables

All the public reports after the approval from the Project Officer will be uploaded in this section. All visitors will have access to the reports and will be able to download them.

2. Newsletter

All the issues of the bi-annual SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Newsletter will be presented in this section. The users will be able to download all the previous issues.

3. Related projects

In this section the visitor will be able to find a list of relevant projects that have established synergy with SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The logos, the title and a link to their website will be offered.

4. Promotional material

This section will host the promotional material produced during the initial stages of the project. All visitors will be able to download the trifold leaflet and the poster.

5. Scientific publications

The scientific publications published in the framework of the project will be listed in this section

Some snapshots from this section are presented below (online [here](#))

Figure 25. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Deliverables page

Newsletter #1

Download

Newsletter #2

Download

Figure 26. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Newsletter page

Figure 27. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Promotional material page

Figure 28. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Scientific publications page

4.2.4 Networking

The Nol is one of the key assets of the project, therefore a separate section is dedicated on the website. This section offers a short description about the concept of the Nol, the benefits from being a Nol member while the visitors can also explore the list of the Nol members. In order to facilitate the registration process to the Nol and engage as many relevant stakeholders as possible, an e-registration process was decided to be designed. Through this specific section the users can be registered as Nol members in a credible, safe but also easy and quick way (online [here](#)).

Figure 29. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Networking page (1)

Three buttons in the page invite the user to i) Discover the Network of Interest and find out a list of the NoI members ii) Join the Network by following the e-registration process or iii) Login to their created profile (Figure 30)

Figure 30. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Networking page (2)

Figure 31. The members of the Network of Interest page

The e - registration follows three different steps that ensure that the process will be GDPR compliant (online [here](#)). In particular:

Step 1: The users will have the opportunity to read the Declaration of Acceptance, as well as the Terms of reference for their participation in the NoI and agree.

Step 2: The users are directed to the information sheet of the activity that gives more information on the project, the activity and the data collection.

Step 3: The users fill in some information (name, e-mail, country, type of stakeholder etc.) and agree on the entries of the consent form.

After following these steps, the user is now registered to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest.

» Step 1	» Step 2	» Step 3
<p>I, the undersigned,</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div> <p>certify that I have read and agree to abide by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest Terms of Reference.</p> <p>I pledge that I will participate in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Nol in my individual capacity and as such, I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium.</p> <p>I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the Nol, unless the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.</p> <p>I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as a SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Nol member as described in the Terms of Reference.</p> <p>I consent that any input or contribution I provide as a member of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Nol may be used by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium for reporting purposes or to align the project's activities with the needs of the relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>I consent to the processing of my personal data needed for my participation in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Nol.</p> <p>AGREE</p>		

Figure 32. Registration process for the Nol _step 1

» Step 1	» Step 2	» Step 3
<h2>1. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Introduction</h2> <p>We would like to invite you to take part in an activity being carried out by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, a 3-year project funded by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe program. Take some time to read this information sheet and if you have questions feel free to reach us.</p> <h3>1.1 What is the SUSTCERTBIOBASED project about?</h3> <p>Biobased products play a prominent role in the transition from a fossil-based economy to a circular economy at an EU and global level. According to an assessment done by the European Commission, biobased products can contribute to a more sustainable economy and could represent approximately €57 billion in annual income and involve 300.000 jobs. But what exactly are biobased products? Biobased products are wholly or partially made from materials of biological origin. Even though they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and offer other advantages such as lower levels of toxicity or novel product characteristics (e.g. biodegradability), it is still very important to ensure their sustainability on environmental, social and economic dimensions.</p> <p>There are plenty of sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels that have been developed to track the sustainability impacts of biobased products. However, given the fact that there is no harmonization of these certification schemes yet, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project</p>		

Figure 33. Registration process for the Nol _step 2

» Step 1
» Step 2
» Step 3

5. Informed Consent Form

I confirm that I understand that by ticking each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked boxes mean that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I also understand that by not giving consent for any of the elements, I may be deemed ineligible for participating in this project's activity.

Required fields are marked with an asterisk (*)

Name*

Lastname*

E-mail*

Figure 34. Registration process for the NoI_step 3

4.2.5 News

The visitors will be updated regarding news from the project and relevant news from the sector. The latest item will be displayed in the Homepage. All partners will support this part of the website with content in order to keep a constant flow of news and articles and maintain this section active throughout the project (online [here](#)).

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Horizon Europe project kicks off!

Brussels, October 18, 2022 – Circular

4.2.6 Events

This section will include the upcoming and the past events that are relevant to the project or the sector. The users will be able to easily get information on relevant events, their relevance, and the date (online [here](#)).

4.2.7 Contact us

The visitors will be able to find the project's contact e-mail, or alternatively to fill in a form to request more information on questions related to the project (online [here](#)).

Figure 35. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Contact us page

4.3 Roles and content management

The dissemination manager (WHITE) designed the structure and the content of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website, while the web-designers (Infoscope Hellas) implemented the platform that went online on 18.10.2022. WHITE will be the main coordinator of the website being responsible for:

- Editing/changing the content at an ad hoc basis
- Check the quality of the material that is uploaded on the website
- Monitor the website Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), update the D&C strategy and give specific advice to the consortium to reach the targets.

Although WHITE will be the main responsible for the smooth operation of the site, all partners are expected to support with relevant content. They will do so in order to ensure that it will remain active throughout the project and will engage relevant stakeholders and the broader public.

Some of the actions that all partners will contribute to, include but are not limited to:

- Dissemination of the website through their networks to increase visibility
- Identification of interesting and relevant events from the sector
- Identification of content for the News section
- Draft articles relevant to the sector and the specific project activities (e.g. events, workshops, major outcomes etc.)
- Provide input when requested (e.g. photos etc.)
- Identification of dissemination opportunities

The website content will be in English and all the uploaded material (reports, articles etc.) will be freely available and accessible to all the visitors.

Google Analytics will be used to keep track of the website's key performance indicators such as the number of visitors or the number of downloads etc. This information will be useful in order to assess the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy and proceed to modifications - if necessary - with the aim to reach our targets and engage as many stakeholders as possible.

4.4 Privacy Policy

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website will be transparent and is committed to protect the users' personal data based on the GDPR regulation. More specifically, a privacy policy applies to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's project website and governs personal data collection and use by the website only. The privacy policy explains the following:

- How we collect personal data
- What types of data we collect
- Bases of lawful processing
- What we do with personal data
- How we secure personal data and when we process them
- If we share personal data with third parties
- If we transfer personal data outside the European Economic Area.
- If we use cookies
- Users' rights
- How long do we retain personal data
- Disclaimer of liability for third party websites
- Children

The privacy policy will be revised at any time and the most recent and updated version will be always uploaded in our website indicating the date since which the current version is active.

“The privacy policy will be always easily accessible by the users in the website footer.”

5. Social Media Accounts

The online presence of the project will be also dependent on the SMAs. Since nowadays SMAs constitute a major news source and marketing channel for the majority of the people, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will maintain an active flow of posts in its accounts.

Four different social media platforms have been selected with the aim to reach citizens with different backgrounds, engage a large variety of stakeholders and maximise the project’s impact. WHITE will be responsible for the management of the SMAs, while all project partners will support with content and will disseminate them through their networks. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SMAs can be found below

Table 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED social media accounts

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED social media		
LinkedIn	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Click here
Twitter	@SUSTCERT4BIO	Click here
Facebook	Sustcert4biobased	Click here
YouTube	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED	Click here

Figure 36. Social media accounts

Figure 37. Recent posts

6. Promotional Video

The promotional video of the project will be developed in M15. The video will be short and concise to attract to the maximum the viewer’s attention and will focus on briefly presenting the project and incentivizing the viewers to search and learn more about the project’s topic and concept.

7. Project's General presentation

A general presentation has been developed to assist partners for introducing SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project in a consistent manner to various audiences and events.

SUST CERT 4 BIOBASED
SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATION FOR BIOBASED SYSTEMS

Presenter
Company
Event

Partners: BUNDESENWALD, G4EVV, ecos, CONTROL4CROSS, European Union

The challenge (1)

- The circular bio-based systems will play a key role in the green transition since they will contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal and particularly its Zero Pollution Action Plan and the 2030 Climate Target Plan.
- To this aim during the last decade the EU heavily invested in a transition from a linear fossil-based economy towards a circular bio-based economy.
- As a result, this ambition accelerated the development of new bio-based products and the creation of numerous bio-based value chains.
- In order to ensure and support this movement from fossil to renewable biological resources, it is critical to secure the environmental, social, and economic sustainability.
- To this aim a plethora of certifications and labels have been developed to allow transparency and comparability of sustainability impacts along the value chains and trade but still there are challenges that hinder their value adoption.

The challenge (2)

In particular:

- There are several **different approaches** regarding the system operating requirements (e.g., sustainability criteria, verification procedures, etc).
- It is **challenging for businesses to select and identify the schemes that are most credible**.
- Different labels put emphasis on **different environmental impacts** of the products.
- Ecological and schemes are **voluntary** therefore their adoption depends on the benefits that could bring to the companies.

Where SUSTCERT4BIOBASED comes into play...

"SUSTCERT4BIOBASED aims to address these challenges by contributing to the assessment of the effectiveness and the robustness of these tools, supporting their harmonization, and recognizing their critical role to ensure a sustainable circular bioeconomy"

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in a nutshell

- The project aims to **develop a monitoring system** to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing certification schemes and labels.
- Will **identify the cost and benefits** of the adoption of certification schemes and labels.
- Will provide **best practices and recommendations** to the project's key stakeholders.
- Through its actions the project will support the **harmonization of system requirements**.
- Improvement and adoption** of sustainability certification schemes and labels.
- Generate insights** of a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable bio-based industry.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Objectives (1)

- To perform a review and **analysis** of existing international and EU **sustainability certification schemes** and business-to-business labels for biological resources and for bio-based materials and products.
- To **gather data** on **global trade flows** for biological resources and for bio-based materials and products, distinguishing between certified and uncertified.
- To define and **optimize a monitoring framework** and indicators for systematic evaluation of the effectiveness and robustness of sustainability schemes and labels.
- To provide a **selection** of certification schemes and labels identified as **"best-practices"** based on the testing of their effectiveness and robustness with the developed monitoring system.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Objectives (2)

- To **generate costs and benefits** (economic and information environmental and social ones) and evaluate the feasibility of interventions in selected industrial bio-based value chains.
- To derive **best practices and recommendations** for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels.
- To establish and maintain continuous **engagement with stakeholders** especially international organizations, industrial partners, science centers, certification bodies and policymakers.

The approach

Who will benefit from the project?

- Government policy industry**
 - Support policies
 - Regulatory framework
 - Market access
- Sustainability system community**
 - Standard and criteria
 - Verification procedures
 - Market access
- Industry**
 - Market access
 - Market demand
 - Market access
- Regional development organizations**
 - Local activities
 - Local demand
 - Local activities

The team

ecirc
ecirc is a research center for circular economy and sustainable business models.

WHITE
WHITE is a research center for white biotechnology and sustainable production.

ecocos
ecocos is a research center for ecological economics and sustainable development.

CONTROL4CROSS
CONTROL4CROSS is a research center for control systems and sustainable production.

Thank you for your time!

Questions

SUST CERT 4 BIOBASED
SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATION FOR BIOBASED SYSTEMS

Figure 38. General presentation (1)

Figure 39. General presentation (2)

8. Publications

Based on the project’s results the partners will proceed and publish scientific papers. In addition, articles, press releases and other news items will be uploaded in the project’s website.

The first published **Press release** of the project is presented below:

Figure 40. First press release

In addition, **a digital Newsletter** will be released bi-annually during the lifetime of the project (in total 6 items will be published). The Newsletter will be automatically sent to the registered subscribers and will be uploaded on the project’s website. The Newsletter will inform all recipients about the progress of the project, the project events and interesting news from related projects and the sector.

WHITE will be responsible for releasing the Newsletter, but all partners will provide content and will disseminate the issues to relevant stakeholders aiming to increase the number of subscribers and followers.

9. Conclusions

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED will deploy its activities to contribute towards the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems. To reach its goals and maximise the impact of its results, the dissemination and communication of the project's outcomes will play a pivotal role. The developed promotional material that is presented in this report will assist the consortium partners to successfully disseminate and communicate the project's progress and breakthroughs to the relevant stakeholders. Other ad hoc material such as infographics, factsheets etc. may be produced within the duration of the project when deemed necessary.

10. Annex

Annex I – Website’s privacy policy

This Privacy Policy applies to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project website and governs personal data collection and use by the website only. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project is committed to being transparent and to ensuring your privacy is protected. By using our website, you consent to personal data practices described below. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project Privacy Policy is effective from 18.10.2022. We reserve the right to update or change the policy at any time, therefore you may want to review it periodically.

1. How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly. We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
- an individual registers to attend in meetings and/or events (e.g. conferences, webinars, etc.) we host and during attendance at such events;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organised and performed by us.

Indirectly. We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g. LinkedIn).

2. What types of data we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **contact details** (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);
- **professional information** (job title, organisation, field of expertise);
- **demographics** (e.g. age, gender, nationality);
- **information about what a person knows or believes.**
- **videos and photos** (from people that attend our events).

3. Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

Legal obligations – for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation, as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

Consent – for processing activities such as organisation of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project’s results.

Contractual obligations – for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project’s publicity obligations.

4. What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys);
- Disseminating our project's results to different types of stakeholders;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

5. How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of/ all our partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

6. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft Teams, Google Drive);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission, according to our relevant contractual obligations.

7. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and/or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

8. Do we use cookies?

Our website uses cookies. A statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies. Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site. You can control and/ or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to

manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a site. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

We use tools like Google Analytics to better understand how visitors interact with our website. This provides us with important information to enable the site to work better. The information collected is not linked to your personal data. For more information on the cookies set by Google Analytics, please visit: <http://code.google.com/apis/analytics/docs/concepts/gaConceptsCookies.html>

The following cookies are used by Google Analytics:

Name	Typical content	Cookie expires after
_ga	Used to distinguish users	2 years
_gat	Used to throttle request rate	1 minute
_gid	Used to distinguish users	24 hours

9. Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by e-mail info@sustcert4biobased.eu. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection, and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask you for some kind of identification (e.g. photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized revealing your personal data. If, due to the complexity of

the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

10. How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we are obliged to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the project's end (unless auditors request further retention). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data securely.

11. Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used and disclosed by these sites.

12. Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

13. Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 18.10.2022 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time. The current version will always be uploaded to our website indicating the date of entry into force, so you know when the most recent revision took place. If there are critical changes in this Policy or our personal data practices change significantly in the future, we will notify you by posting the changes on our website.

Annex II- Network of Interest online registration documents

Declaration of Acceptance for the Network of Interest

Declaration of Acceptance

(for individuals appointed as members of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI)

I, the undersigned, _____ certify that I have read and agree to abide by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest Terms of Reference.

I pledge that I will participate in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI in my individual capacity and as such, I may not delegate another person to carry out the work or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement with the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium.

I undertake not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the NoI, unless the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium agrees to release me from this obligation, and to respect the confidentiality requirements.

I declare to accept entirely and with no reservations my appointment as a SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI member as described in the Terms of Reference.

I consent that any input or contribution I provide as a member of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI may be used by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium for reporting purposes or to align the project's activities with the needs of the relevant stakeholders.

I consent to the processing of my personal data needed for my participation in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI.

NoI Terms of reference

Introduction

You have been invited to become part of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest. This document includes the terms of reference and will assist you to understand what your involvement in the NoI will include before you decide to participate. Please take some time to read carefully the document. In case you have questions, you can always contact us at info@sustcert4biobased.eu.

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in a nutshell

In the transition from a linear fossil-based economy towards a circular biobased economy, numerous biobased value chains have been set up at different levels of development, and several new biobased products have been introduced to the market. Biobased products are wholly or partially derived from biological resources, but still, it is important to ensure their sustainability considering the range of environmental impacts, as well as to ensure their social and economic sustainability.

To this end, a plethora of sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels have been developed to allow traceability and transparency of sustainability impacts along the value chains and trades. Today, it is essential to evaluate the credibility of these tools and support their harmonization. This is where SUSTCERT4BIOBASED comes into play!

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED aims to develop a monitoring system to assess the effectiveness, robustness and completeness of the existing certification schemes and labels, identify their strengths and weaknesses and promote the adoption of the best-in-class certification schemes and labels. The interdisciplinary consortium will also be reviewing and analysing the existing sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels; creating a database of global trade flows for biological resources and biobased products, and carrying out costs and benefits analysis from the adoption of certification schemes and labels in selected industrial biobased value chains. In this vein, the consortium will engage a variety of relevant stakeholders such as international organisations, industrial biobased value chain actors, scheme owners, certifications bodies, regional bioeconomy actors, and policy makers, and will offer recommendations for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels.

Project Partners

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED brings together 5 partners across 4 European countries as follows:

	<p style="text-align: center;">Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) https://www.wur.nl/</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">WR is part of Wageningen University & Research in the Netherlands that carries out application-oriented and field-based research in the domain of 'healthy food and living environment' for governments and the business community at large.</p>
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	<p>Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)</p> <p>https://www.fcirce.es/en/</p>	<p>CIRCE is a multidisciplinary technology transfer center that specialises in innovation and sustainable development solutions.</p>
	<p>White Research SRL (WHITE)</p> <p>https://white-research.eu/</p>	<p>WHITE is a boutique research and consulting company, providing services to the public and private sector, academia and civil society organisations. White specialises in research services and business consulting, communications and stakeholder engagement as well as in EU studies and EU funding services.</p>
	<p>Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)</p> <p>https://ecostandard.org/</p>	<p>ECOS is an international NGO with a network of members and experts advocating for environmentally friendly technical standards, policies and laws.</p>
	<p>Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)</p> <p>https://controlunion-germany.com/</p>	<p>Control Union Certifications has focused its efforts on developing services around the sustainability of the industry's supply chains which feed into the food, feed, forestry, biomass, bioenergy, social compliance and textiles markets.</p>

Role and benefits

Role

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of interest will engage a wide range of stakeholders to facilitate the international networking, dialogue and knowledge exchange across industrial biobased value chain actors and the sustainability system community.

The role of the NoI would be to interact, receive project updates, inform about recent advancements and trends, and share their knowledge and views on bioeconomy-related aspects. The NoI members will be invited to meetings and events such as biannual online meetings, where the main findings of

the project will be presented, and they will have the chance to provide feedback based on their expertise. They will also be invited to participate in workshops and other events that might be organised during the project's lifecycle. Additionally, Nol members might be invited to talk about their expertise, promote the project's activities and results, or participate in future dissemination and communication actions during the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. In that way, their participation could contribute to triggering cross-disciplinary dialogue, stimulating interaction with target actors and associations as well as helping build trust among the range of stakeholders.

Lastly, they could be subscribed to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED newsletter and project partners could pool the Nol expertise on an ad-hoc basis according to the needs of the project.

Benefits

Some of the benefits of participation in the Nol would be to:

- Connect with other individuals and organisations interested in bioeconomy and sustainability certifications/labels.
- Participate in the bi-annual online meetings to interact with other participants and discuss various issues from the sector and the project
- Participate in events and workshops organised by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project
- Receive project updates
- Share their knowledge and views on bioeconomy certification-related aspects
- Receive the biannual newsletter which will contain interesting news on SUSTCERT4BIOBASED and more

Terms of membership

Membership

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Nol is expected to be composed of at least 50 members and will be consisted of key stakeholders. Although individual members of the Nol may be selected because of their affiliations with key organisations, they will serve on the Nol in their individual capacity to represent the interests and views of their stakeholder communities. Equally, members of the Nol may not delegate another person to carry out the role expected from them or be replaced by any other person without prior written agreement.

Members of the Nol are appointed for the duration of the project (36 months, from 1 June 2022 to 31 May 2025).

Although active engagement is expected, participation in the Nol activities is entirely voluntary. There will be no adverse consequences if a Nol member decides not to participate or withdraw at any stage. In fact, Nol members may withdraw their participation at any time by informing the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest Manager (White Research). They may as well request to withdraw their data without giving a reason and without prejudice. Anonymous data already collected will be used because we cannot trace the information back to a specific person, but no further data or input will be collected, nor any other procedure will be carried out in relation to the specific member.

Stakeholders who agree to join the Nol will be requested to sign the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Declaration of Acceptance (DoA), according to which they will commit to:

- abide by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI Terms of Reference (as presented herein);
- participate in the NoI in their individual capacity and not delegate another person to carry out any expected work without a prior written agreement;
- agree not to divulge any information given in the context of the work of the NoI and respect the confidentiality requirements;
- agree that any input or contribution they provide as members of the NoI may be used by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED for reporting purposes and/or to align the project's activities and results.

Management

The Network of Interest is managed by the Network of Interest Manager (White Research). The Network of Interest (NoI) Manager facilitates the interactions between the consortium and the NoI in order to ensure that the members will not be overloaded. The NoI manager is also responsible for arranging the biannual NoI meetings.

Contact point

Any further information, complaint, or concern about any aspect of your experience as a member of the NoI could be addressed to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest Manager (White Research), who oversees the setting up and the management of the NoI, by using the details provided below:

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI Manager: White Research SRL

Contact Person: Annie Kalimeri

Phone: +32 2 520 00 09

Email: akalimeri@white-research.eu

Project Website: sustcert4biobased.eu

Information Sheet and consent form

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Introduction

We would like to invite you to take part in an activity being carried out by the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, a 3-year project funded by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe program. Take some time to read this information sheet and if you have questions feel free to reach us.

What is the SUSTCERTBIOBASED project about?

Biobased products play a prominent role in the transition from a fossil-based economy to a circular economy at an EU and global level. According to an assessment done by the European Commission, biobased products can contribute to a more sustainable economy and could represent approximately €57 billion in annual income and involve 300.000 jobs.¹

But what exactly are biobased products? Biobased products are wholly or partially made from materials of biological origin. Even though they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and offer other advantages such as lower levels of toxicity or novel product characteristics (e.g. biodegradability), it is still very important to ensure their sustainability on environmental, social and economic dimensions.

There are plenty of sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels that have been developed to track the sustainability impacts of biobased products. However, given the fact that there is no harmonization of these certification schemes yet, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will contribute to defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainable certification schemes and business-to-business labels. The project will lay the foundation to support a faster and smoother transition to a circular, sustainable bioeconomy!

It will do so by developing a monitoring system to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of existing certification schemes and labels and assessing the feasibility of adoption of certification schemes and labels by taking into consideration costs and benefits (including internalized environmental and social ones). The results of the project as well as the insights gained along the way will be used to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policymakers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. Within the next years the multidisciplinary consortium of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project will organise several events and workshops to inform the audience about important findings and updates on the progress of the project. Additionally, a Network of Interest consisting of at least 50 members will be developed to facilitate the international networking, dialogue and knowledge exchange across industrial biobased value chain actors and the sustainability system community.

Useful Information

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/biotechnology/bio-based-products_en

Is my participation voluntary and what will it involve?

Your participation in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project is entirely voluntary. If you decide to participate in a SUSTCERT4BIOBASED activity, you will be asked to sign an **Informed Consent Form** to collect and process your data. The project will last for 36 months but your involvement will last as long as you wish.

Purpose of personal data collection

The role of the Network of Interest (NoI) is to provide a platform where members can interact, receive project updates, and share their knowledge and views on bioeconomy and sustainability certification related aspects. To effectively conduct this, we would need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details;
- Demographics (age, gender, country of origin)
- Professional information (where you are working, what is your job position, which is the area of your expertise)
- Personal opinions on the topic

What we will do with your data

The information you provide is **confidential**. Your name and professional information (role, expertise) will be visible in our website in the list of Network of Interest members. Your consent form will be kept separate from the observations collected during the course of the project activity. We will share your data with other SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project partners that are involved in the data analysis and reporting process. Once the data is analysed, a report of the findings may be submitted for publication. The project's deliverables that will be derived by this activity will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. The results of this project activity might be also shared with European Union representatives (e.g., the Project Officer evaluating the project's progress, auditing EU agencies). Only broad trends will be reported, and **it will not be possible to identify any individuals**.

Are there any risks involved?

No, there are no risks involved.

Access, deletion of information, or consent withdrawal

According to the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), you have the right to request:

- I. a copy of your data;
- II. correction of your data, if you think they are not accurate;
- III. to delete your data;
- IV. to limit or stop processing your personal data;
- V. to give you your data in an appropriate format and transfer them to another organisation.

You can also withdraw your consent and, therefore, your participation at any time without consequences. In case of anonymous data already collected, keep in mind that will be used since we cannot trace the information back to you. Further data would not be collected, or any other procedure would not be carried out in relation to your information.

In case you wish to verify the personal data we store, to modify, correct, delete or request a consent withdrawal you may communicate with the responsible partner listed below.

Contact Information

Partner name: WHITE RESEARCH SRL

e-mail: info@sustcert4biobased.eu

Website: sustcert4biobased.eu

Informed Consent Form

I confirm that I understand that by ticking each box below I am consenting to this element of the study. I understand that it will be assumed that unticked boxes mean that I DO NOT consent to that part of the study. I also understand that by not giving consent for any of the elements, I may be deemed ineligible for participating in this project's activity.

I confirm that I have been given an explanation of the purpose of the project's activities. I have read and understood the Information Sheet which I was provided with or listened to an explanation about the project by a project partner.

I have had an opportunity to consider what kind of information will be expected of me. I have also had the opportunity to ask questions and clarifications about the requested information which have been answered to my satisfaction.

I agree to provide my name, role and name of the organisation I belong and I am aware that I will appear on the project's website.

I agree to receive the project's biannual Newsletter with the project's updates.

I agree to appear in pictures/videos that might be taken during project activities as evidence of any activity itself and as promotional material for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. I understand that these pictures will not be provided to any organisation for commercial purposes. However, they may be processed by third parties as a consequence of their dissemination at international level through the project's social media and website.

I understand that the consortium has no control on the images after dissemination.

I agree that my anonymised research data may be used by others for future research (I will not be identifiable when this data is shared).

I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason, and that any data after the time of which it is withdrawn will be no longer included as part of any future reports, unless I agree.

I understand that my personal data will be held and processed in confidence and in accordance with the principles laid out by GDPR.

I am aware of whom I should contact if I wish to lodge a complaint.

I confirm that I have read and understood the above information and freely consent to participate in activities of the project. I have been given adequate time to consider my participation.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced, and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.fcirce.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

CONTACT US

info@sustcert4biobased.eu

- Sustcert4biobased
- @SUSTCERT4BIO
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
- SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

VISIT

www.sustcert4biobased.eu